

NDAC/LO/055

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The Cowling globals in Step 2/3, erratum.

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1. Introduction

In NDAC/LO/034, I reported about the determinacy of global parameters in ~~the~~ Step 2/3 solution. In particular, the space-time metric coefficients defined by Cowling (1983) were tested in small-scale simulations. When this work was continued with the new ACCU23/SOLV23 routines, the earlier results for the Cowling parameters could not be reproduced, and a serious error was discovered in the old programs. The present note gives some preliminary new results, as obtained from simulated solutions with 730 and 1095 sets (1 - 1.5 years of observations). The definitions and differential coefficients for the Cowling parameters are correctly given in NDAC/LO/034, and the old numbering (g_{13} - g_{27}) is also used.

2. Selection of global parameters

As before, one group of global parameters consists of the twelve Fourier coefficients $\sin/\cos n\Psi$, where Ψ is the solar aspect angle $\nu - \nu_0$. The fifteen Cowling parameters can not all be determined by HIPPARCOS, even if the Fourier sine-terms are left out. From studies of the covariance matrix of the solutions, as well as of the eigenvectors of the normal equations, one may define the following simple set of "compound" Cowling parameters:

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &\equiv g_{13} + g_{14} + 2 g_{15} & c_5 &\equiv g_{23} \\ c_2 &\equiv g_{16} + g_{17} - g_{18} & c_6 &\equiv g_{24} - 0.5 g_{27} \\ c_3 &\equiv g_{20} + g_{21} & c_7 &\equiv g_{25} \\ c_4 &\equiv g_{22} & c_8 &\equiv g_{26} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

This is not the theoretical optimum, but with simple coefficients, the mutual correlations are reasonable small. Finally, the correlation to the first-order aberration may also be included (g_{28}).

3. Theoretical mean errors

As before, a mean global mean error is defined by g_2 - g_{12} , and the formula

$$\sigma_o^{glob} = \text{Const. } \sigma_v (N_{eff}^{glob})^{-0.5} \quad (2)$$

remains valid with

$$N_{eff}^{glob} = \text{nobs} - \text{naspar} \times \text{nstar} - \text{nset} - \text{nglob} \quad (3)$$

(In NDAC/LO/034, the number of astrometric parameters, naspar, was equal to three). The constant in (2) seems to depend slightly on both nset and naspar, and may preliminarily be estimated at about 1.7 for the full 2.5-year mission with naspar = 5.

It remains to give the relative errors for the individual globals. It is then important not to include highly correlated parameters, and there are two main options. We may either leave c_1 and c_2 out and determine g_1 - g_{12} , c_3 - c_8 (case "A" in Table 1). If the Fourier-terms are small, c_1 and c_2 may be determined instead of g_1 , g_3 , ..., g_{11} as in case "B". In case A, we are left with large correlations for c_5 and c_8 relative to g_1 . This (sin Ψ -) term is always strongly correlated with the parallaxes, and may never be well determined. Instead of making a (possibly spurious) large correction, it is probably better to leave g_1 always out. This gives the results in column A1.

Table 1. Mean errors relative to σ_o^{glob}

	A	A1	B
g_1	190	-	-
g_2	1.26	1.26	1.26
g_3	0.90	0.90	-
g_4	1.02	1.02	1.02
g_5	0.89	0.89	-
g_6	1.01	1.01	1.01
g_7	0.92	0.92	-
g_8	1.04	1.04	1.04
g_9	0.96	0.96	-
g_{10}	1.07	1.07	1.07
g_{11}	1.00	1.00	-
g_{12}	0.92	0.92	0.92
c_1	-	-	0.93
c_2	-	-	1.08
c_3	0.34	0.34	0.34
c_4	2.6	2.5	2.5
c_5	4.3	2.4	2.4
c_6	3.0	3.0	3.0
c_7	4.6	4.6	4.6
c_8	5.7	4.8	4.8

When one includes the aberration, there is a large correlation (-.82) with c_3 . In effect, the well-determined parameter is not c_3 , but $c_3 + 0.3 g_{28}$. Similarly, in case B, c_1 and c_2 are correlated, and we may determine the combination $c_1 + 0.75 c_2$ with relative error about 0.87.

4. Conclusions

The only space-time parameter that is ideally suited for determination by HIPPARCOS is $c_3 \equiv g_{20} + g_{21}$. For the full mission, one may estimate $\sigma_0^{glob} \approx 0.006$ mas, and thus c_3 will be determined to within about 10^{-11} . If c_1 and c_2 can be reliably determined at all (that is, if most Fourier-terms turn out to be negligibly small), their minimum errors are some three times larger. The standard GR light-deflection is given by g_{13} alone, and if g_{15} - g_{18} are set to zero, the GR-deflection might be measurable to this accuracy (about 0.1 %).

For c_4 - c_8 , the errors are of the order 10^{-10} , which is probably above any reasonable space-time effects. These terms are uncorrelated with the Fourier ones, however, and they may at least be used in tests for subtle instrumental distortions.